

CARBON FIBER REINFORCED TIN-SUPERCONDUCTOR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Unidirectional and continuous carbon fiber tin-matrix composites were used for the packaging of the high-temperature superconductor $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ by diffusion bonding at 1700°C and 500 psi. Tin served as the adhesive and to increase the ductility, the normal-state electrical conductivity and the thermal conductivity. Carbon fibers served to increase the strength and the modulus, both in tension along the fiber direction and in compression perpendicular to the fiber layers, and also served to increase the thermal conductivity and the thermal fatigue resistance. At 24 vol.% fibers, the tensile strength was approximately equal to the compressive strength. With further increase of the fiber content, the tensile strength exceeded the compressive strength, reaching 134 MPa at 31 vol.% fibers. For fiber contents less than 30 vol.% fibers, the compressive ductility exceeded that of the plain superconductor. At 30 vol.% fibers, the tensile modulus reached 10 GPa. The tensile load was essentially sustained by the carbon fibers and the superconducting behavior was maintained after tension almost to the point of tensile fracture.

INTRODUCTION

The high T_c superconductors are brittle, hard to shape, and high in normal-state electrical resistivity. On the other hand, metals are in general ductile, formable, low in electrical resistivity and high in thermal conductivity. Therefore, the combination of a superconductor and a metal in the form of a composite material is attractive [1-5].

Because brittle ceramics are much stronger in compression than in tension, it is necessary to strengthen the composite further, particularly in tension. For this purpose, we have used carbon fibers, because carbon fibers are very strong (especially in tension), nearly zero in thermal expansion coefficient (valuable for thermal fatigue resistance), very high in thermal conductivity (better than copper), quite low in electrical resistivity and corrosion resistant. We report here that carbon fibers reinforced tin-superconductor composites provide an effective way of packaging ceramic superconductors (in bulk, film or wire form) so that the package exhibits good mechanical, electrical and thermal properties.

FABRICATION

The superconductor was $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$. It was prepared by pressing $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ powder (W.R. Grace and Co., Davison Chemical Division, super T_c -123, code: S-001) at a pressure of 137 MPa and then sintering at 950°C for 12 h, followed by annealing at 420°C in flowing oxygen for 1 h.

The tin used was in the form of foils (Fisher Scientific Co.) containing at least 99.8 wt.% Sn.

The carbon fibers used were continuous, PAN-based (Celion GY-70) and sized, with a tensile modulus of 530 GPa.

The carbon fiber reinforced tin-superconductor composite was prepared by using a two-step process. The first step involved the preparation of a tin-matrix unidirectional carbon fiber composite (abbreviated MMC) by laying up carbon fibers and tin foils in the form of alternate layers and consolidating by hot pressing (by using a hydraulic press) at 5°C above the melting temperature of tin and at a pressure in the range from 8,000 to 10,000 psi (from 55 to 69 MPa) for 10–20 s. The minimum pressure for the first step is about 55 MPa. The second step involved hot pressing a layer of superconductor sandwiched by two layers of MMC at 170°C and 500 psi (4 MPa) for 15 min in order to achieve diffusion bonding. Note that 170°C is below the melting point of tin (232°C). The minimum temperature for the second step is 150°C for composites containing carbon fibers and 100°C for those containing no carbon fibers. The minimum pressure for the second step is about 500 MPa.

CHARACTERIZATION

Fig. 1 shows the dependence of the electrical resistivity on temperature for the plain superconductor (solid circles), for a composite without fibers but containing 80.1 vol.% Sn (open circles), and for a composite containing 32.1 vol.% fiber and 50.2 vol.% Sn (crosses). The drop to zero resistivity is slightly less sharp for either composite than the plain superconductor. Carbon fibers have a lower electrical resistivity than the plain superconductor above T_c , but its value is higher than that of tin. Therefore, the normal-state electrical resistivity of the composite with tin and fibers is lower than that of the plain superconductor and higher than that of the composite with tin and no fiber.

Mechanical testing was performed using a hydraulic Materials Testing System (MTS). The strain in tensile or compressive testing was measured by the displacement of the crosshead. The gage length was 34.7 mm for tensile testing and 6 mm for compressive testing. Compressive testing was performed with the force perpendicular to the laminate layers. Tensile testing was performed with the force parallel to the fibers in the plane of the laminate. At least three samples were run and the data were averaged for each composite composition in each type of test.

Fig. 2 shows the compressive stress-strain curves (up to fracture) for a composite containing tin (24 vol.% Sn) but no fibers (open circles) and a composite containing 51.1 vol.% Sn and 26.2 vol.% fibers (solid circles). Fig. 3 shows the effects of both fiber and tin contents on the compressive ductility. Tin greatly increased the

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Fig. 2 Compressive stress-strain curves (up to fracture) for a composite without fibers (24 vol.% Sn) (open circles) and a composite with fibers (51.1 vol.% Sn and 26.2 vol.% fibers) (solid circles).

Fig. 3 Effects of tin and fiber contents on the compressive ductility.

ductility, but the fibers decreased the ductility. Fig. 4 shows the effects of both tin and fiber contents on the compressive elastic modulus. The decrease of the modulus with increasing tin content and decreasing fiber content is significant. Fig. 5 shows the variation of the compressive strength with the tin and fiber contents. No systematic trend was found, because the strength is very sensitive to small flaws that are bound to be present in the superconductor.

Fig. 6 shows the tensile stress-strain curves (up to fracture) for a composite containing tin (24 vol.% Sn) but no fibers (open circles) and a composite containing 51.4 vol.% Sn and 27.2 vol.% fibers (solid circles). Fig. 7, 8 and 9 show the effects of tin and fiber contents on the tensile test results. The tensile test was performed along the fiber direction. The addition of carbon fibers greatly improved the tensile strength (Fig. 7), but decreased the ductility slightly (Fig. 8). The tensile modulus was increased by increasing the fiber content. Debonding between the MMC and the superconductor and some fiber pull-out were observed from the fracture surface after the tensile test.

Fig. 4 Effects of tin and fiber contents on the compressive elastic modulus.

Fig. 5 Effects of tin and fiber contents on the compressive strength.

Fig. 6 Tensile stress-strain curves (up to fracture) for a composite without fibers (24 vol.% Sn) (open circles) and a composite with fibers (51.4 vol.% Sn and 27.2 vol.% fibers) (solid circles).

Fig. 7 Effects of tin and fiber contents on the tensile strength.

Fig. 8 Effects of tin and fiber contents on the tensile ductility.

Fig. 9 Effects of tin and fiber contents on the tensile modulus.

Table 1 Thermal fatigue due to cycling between room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature

Carbon fiber content (vol.%)	Sn content (vol.%)	No. of cycles for delamination to start*
0	43.2	63
3.0	39.4	86
8.3	40.1	102
12.0	43.1	116
15.3	48.3	123
20.1	50.2	127

*Each number is the average of three specimens

A composite containing 31.0 vol.% fibers and 50.2 vol.% tin was subjected to tension up to a tensile stress of 90.6 MPa and a tensile strain of 0.91% (below the stress or strain required for fracture) and then the load was released (allowing the strain to return to essentially zero) and the electrical resistivity was measured as a function of temperature. It remained superconducting.

Composites of various fiber contents were subjected to thermal cycling between room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K) by immersion in liquid nitrogen for 20 min, followed by room temperature equilibration for at least 30 min, and repeating. After every cycle, each specimen was observed under an optical microscope to look for delamination (slight cracking) between the superconductor and the MMC. Table 1 shows the number of cycles for the start of delamination for each composite composition. The higher was the carbon fiber content, the greater was the number of cycles for the start of delamination.

CONCLUSION

The combination of tin and continuous carbon fibers was found to be effective for packaging ceramic superconductors so as to render them mechanically durable and electrically and thermally stable. The process involved diffusion bonding of the superconductor between two layers of a tin-matrix carbon fiber composite. Tin served as the adhesive and also served to increase the ductility, the normal-state electrical conductivity and the thermal conductivity. Carbon fibers served to increase the strength and the modulus, both in tension (parallel to the fibers) and in compression (perpendicular to the fiber layers), they also served to increase the thermal conductivity and the thermal fatigue resistance. The tensile load was essentially sustained by the carbon fibers and the superconducting behavior was maintained after tension almost to the point of fracture.

REFERENCES

1. In-Gann Chen, S. Sen and D.M. Stefanescu, Appl. Phys. Lett. 52 (16), 1355 (1988).
2. F.H. Streitz, M.Z. Cieplak, Gang Xiao, A. Gavrin, A. Bakhshai and C.L. Chien, Appl. Phys. Lett. 52, 927 (1988).
3. A. Goyal, P.D. Funkenbusch, G.C.S. Chang and S.J. Burns, Mater. Lett. 6(8-9), 257 (1988).
4. R.W. McCallum, J.D. Verhoeven, M.A. Noack, E.D. Gibson, F.C. Laabs and D.K. Finnemore, Advanced Ceramic Materials 2 (3B), 388 (1987).
5. S. Jin, R.C. Sherwood, R.B. Van Dover, T.H. Tiefel and D.W. Johnson, Jr., Appl. Phys. Lett. 51, 203 (1987).